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Social structures, social institutions and way of life

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МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Xodjayev Sobir KEKSALIK VA ERTA QARISH SOTSIOGERONTOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA.....	4
2. To‘raxo‘jayeva Ra‘no DAVLAT XIZMATCHILARINI KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH AHOLI ORASIDAGI NOROZILIK KAYFIYATINI OLDINI OLISH MEHANIZMI SIFATIDA.....	11
3. Turdikulov Shuxrat SOG‘LIQNI SAQLASH SOHASIDA KORRUPSIYAGA QARSHI KURASHISHNING INSTITUTIONAL YONDASHUVI.....	19
4. Mo‘minov Zokirjon ZAMONAVIY SOTSIOLOGIYA:IJTIMOIIY O‘ZGARISHLARDA MOBILLIK.....	26
5. Xoliqnazarov Rashidjon DUNYO VA MDH DAVLATLARI IJTIMOIIY HAYOTIDA ELEKTRON HUJJAT AYLANISH TIZIMINING O‘RNI.....	33
6. Shokirov Shaxrizod HUQUQBUZARLIK VA JINOYATCHILIKNING OLDINI OLISHDA JAMOATCHILIK FIKRINI TA‘SIRI BO‘YICHA XALQARO TAJRIBA TAHLILI.....	41
7. Nurullayeva Umida XOTIN-QIZLARNI RAHBARLIK LAVOZIMLARIGA KO‘TARILISHI: TO‘SIQLAR VA IMKONIYATLAR.....	51
8. Nazarova Nilufar STRUCTURAL-FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF ENSURING PROFESSIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF YOUTH OF UZBEKISTAN.....	62
9. A‘zamova Kumush INSON QADRINI YUKSALTIRISHDA REGULYATIV FUNKSIYALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	72
10. Ixtiyarov Farxod INSON KAPITALINI KEYS METODI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHNI TADQIQ ETISH: ASOSIIY TUSHUNCHA VA QONUNIYATLAR.....	78
11. Karimova Maftuna RIVOJLANGAN DAVLATLARNING UMUMIIY TA‘LIM MUASSALARIDA BOLALAR ZO‘RAVONLIGINI OLDINI OLISHGA QARATILGAN CHORA –TADBIRLAR.....	90
12. Butoyev Ilxom SOG‘LOM TURMUSH TARZINI SHAKLLANISHIDA MA‘NAVIYAT TARBIYASINING TUTGAN O‘RNI.....	98
13. Bozorova O‘lmasxon YOSHLAR III RENESSANS MA'RIFIY STRATEGIYASINING HARAKATLANTIRUVCHI KUCHI.....	103

ИЖТИМОЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF SOCIAL STUDIES

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STRUCTURAL-FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF ENSURING PROFESSIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF YOUTH OF UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATION

The purpose of this study is to carry out a structural-functional analysis of ensuring the professional competitiveness of young people in Uzbekistan. An empirical, frequency-based sociological survey was conducted. In it (n=723 people; 50.5% of respondents are men and 49.5% are women; 321 people live in the city (44.4%), 246 people (34%) live in rural areas, and 156 people (21.6%) live in the district center) students participated. Due to the improvement of the education sector and educational activities in Uzbekistan, the importance of the state policy affecting the formation of human capital among young people and their level of competitiveness is increasing. It is highlighted that the functional and institutional practical role of the family in the formation of competitive qualities in young people is significant. Factors that have a positive impact on the development of competitiveness of young people: support of initiative, provision of quality education, acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications were ranked high. Factors that have a negative impact on the development of professional competitiveness: corrupt situations, inappropriate conflicts in labor activity, low-quality education, low-income work, etc. are mentioned as obstacles. Because of the research, it is necessary to develop a theoretical model of the formation of competitiveness qualities and achieve its practical application.

Keywords: quality of competitiveness, professional training, competitive environment, quality of education, family environment.

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O'ZBEKISTON YOSHLARINING PROFESSIONAL AQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING TARKIBIY-FUNKSIONAL TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi O'zbekistonda yoshlarning kasbiy raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlashning tarkibiy-funksional tahlilini o'tkazishdan iborat. Empirik, chastotaga asoslangan sotsiologik so'rov o'tkazildi. Unda (n=723 kishi; respondentlarning 50,5 foizi erkaklar va 49,5 foizi ayollar; 321 nafari shaharda (44,4 foiz), 246 nafari (34 foizi) qishloqlarda, 156 nafari (21,6 foizi) tuman markazida istiqomat qiladi) talabalari ishtirok etishdi. O'zbekistonda ta'lim sohasi va ta'lim

faoliyati takomillashib borishi munosabati bilan yoshlar o'rtasida inson kapitalini shakllantirish va ularning raqobatbardoshlik darajasini oshirishga ta'sir etuvchi davlat siyosatining ahamiyati ortib bormoqda. Yoshlarda raqobatbardosh fazilatlarni shakllantirishda oilaning funksional va institutsional amaliy ahamiyati katta ekanligi ta'kidlangan. Yoshlarning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar: tashabbusni qo'llab-quvvatlash, sifatli ta'lim berish, bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni egallash kabilar yuqori o'ringa qo'yildi. Kasbiy raqobatbardoshlikni rivojlantirishga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar: korruptsion holatlar, mehnat faoliyatidagi nomaqbul nizolar, sifatsiz ta'lim, kam daromadli mehnat va hokazolar to'sqinlik qiladi. Tadqiqotlar tufayli raqobatbardoshlik sifatlarini shakllantirishning nazariy modelini ishlab chiqish va uni amaliy qo'llashga erishish lozim.

Kalit so'zlar: raqobatbardoshlik sifati, kasbiy tayyorgarlik, raqobat muhiti, ta'lim sifati, oilaviy muhit.

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СТРУКТУРНО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ МОЛОДЕЖИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Целью данного исследования является проведение структурно-функционального анализа обеспечения профессиональной конкурентоспособности молодежи Узбекистана. Проведен эмпирический частотный социологический опрос. В исследовании (n=723 чел.; 50,5 % опрошенных мужчин и 49,5 % женщин; в городе проживает 321 чел. (44,4 %), в сельской местности проживает 246 чел. (34 %), проживает 156 чел. (21,6 %) в райцентре) участвовали студенты. В связи с совершенствованием сферы образования и образовательной деятельности в Узбекистане возрастает значение государственной политики, влияющей на формирование человеческого капитала у молодежи и уровень ее конкурентоспособности. Подчеркнуто, что функциональная и институционально-практическая роль семьи в формировании конкурентоспособных качеств у молодежи значительна. Факторы, оказывающие положительное влияние на развитие конкурентоспособности молодежи: поддержка инициативы, предоставление качественного образования, получение знаний, навыков и квалификации получили высокую оценку. В качестве препятствий называются факторы, негативно влияющие на развитие профессиональной конкурентоспособности: коррупционные ситуации, неуместные конфликты в трудовой деятельности, некачественное образование, малооплачиваемая работа и т.п. В связи с исследованием необходимо разработать теоретическую модель формирования качеств конкурентоспособности и добиться ее практического применения.

Ключевые слова: качество конкурентоспособности, профессиональная подготовка, конкурентная среда, качество образования, семейная среда.

INTRODUCTION.

Among the factors that determine the development of society, the issue of youth is of particular importance. In particular, the issue of training them to be professionally competitive, creating suitable living conditions for them to realize their abilities and talents, and forming competitive qualities in them is urgent. From this point of view, it is important to study the issue of formation of professional competitiveness of young people [10; 13; 14; 19].

Competitiveness is expressed through training in certain contests, competing in various fields, in which a certain professional activity such as studying, gaining knowledge, work, strengthening one's position in the work team, self-expression, high results in the organizational hierarchy or

occupying positions it is shown through successes [11. 70-73; 12. 40-44]. The concepts of competition and competitiveness are studied not only in economic theory, but also in political science, pedagogy, sociology, and psychology.

LITERATURE REVIEW.

In the conditions of today's globalization, the understanding of the content of competitiveness in the professional activity of young personnel, the study of the quality of professional training through sociological research is becoming urgent. Therefore, in New Uzbekistan, special attention is being paid to the conditions for realizing the professional potential of graduates of higher educational institutions and young professionals [14. 25-28]. In particular, in accordance with the concept of development of higher education: "to develop public-private partnership in the field of higher education, to increase the level of coverage with higher education from 50 percent based on the organization of activities of state and non-state higher education institutions in the regions, to create a healthy competitive environment in the field" [28] defined. As a result, 24 foreign and 27 non-state universities were established by supporting competition in higher education and attracting the private sector. On this basis, the level of coverage of youth with higher education was increased from 9 percent to 32 percent" [29].

In order to analyze the competitiveness of the human potential of young people, it is necessary to determine the factors that determine the composition of competitiveness and their content. First, it is necessary to take into account the quality of education, that is, the formation of human capital in young people due to the improvement of the field of education and educational activities, as well as the impact on their level of competitiveness. It is known that there is a growing demand for specialists who have graduated from the most prestigious universities in the world (for example, TNE - The Times Higher Education World University Rankings, QS - Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, ARWU - Academic Ranking of World Universities, The U.S. News and World Report - Best Global University Rankings). In this regard, "2 higher educational institutions, including the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers, rose 40 places (from last year's 251st place) to 211+ places in the ranking of universities of Eastern European and Central Asian countries in 2022 by the QS-international rating company. National University of Uzbekistan rose by 100 places and got 251+ places (from last year's 351st place)" [29].

Secondly, employers in the same conditions evaluate the main characteristics of young talented professionals. In turn, innate abilities are determined based on a different level of human capital. In this case, the factor of family institution is considered important, family capital affects the development of innate abilities, as well as the increase of human capital through education. Therefore, the level of competitiveness of young professionals is strongly influenced by the family environment [6. 140-146; 7. 14-20], where the higher the family income and the education of parents, the higher the individual's level of competitiveness is empirically based through sociological research. By the amount of investment allocated to the child by parents or other relatives and through proper guidance, today's youth can learn various foreign languages, computer programs (Web programmers, Digital Designers), mathematics (SAT, GMAT, GRE tests) and they can get certain achievements in different fields along with deep mastering of such subjects. This makes the theoretical research of the family environment and socialization more relevant.

A person becomes socialized in the family environment. It covers aspects related to the human factor, education, skills, experience, the balance of the external and internal world of a person, and its physical, psychological, social, and spiritual aspects. Therefore, the family environment as a social factor is an important basis for a person's ability to work, social activity, improving his professional skills, satisfaction with his family and social status, and setting realistic life plans.

M. Kuronov and O. Bozorov expressed their opinion on the functional and institutional practical aspect of the family in the formation of competitive qualities in young people: "The family, as an important part of the social environment, plays a big role in the upbringing of young people, in what kind of people they will become in the future. In this, the role of father and mother is incomparable. Because it is in this place that the fundamentals of early education and the attitude to values are decided, and it is impossible not to take into account that the result of education is

connected with the fate of the whole nation, the country" [21. 32-33]. In fact, the family institution is considered important in the formation of youth competitiveness. Because in the system of relationships such as "youth - family", "youth - education", "youth - society", family, family environment and enlightenment in the family directly affect the formation of competitive qualities in young people. In this regard, T. Parsons looks at the family as a social system institution, "the family is a well-organized and integrated group, a community in the social system, and at the same time, an institution that performs an integral function in the social system, an element of the normative structure of the cultural system" [3. 646-650; 4. 1005-1009; 5. 29-33; 23. 731-732]. After all, the family fulfills educational, goal-directing, mobilizing, adapting, recreational, procreative, psychotherapeutic tasks, and at its core is ensuring the maturity of young people. In these respects, the family differs from other social institutions.

Conducting a unified state policy aimed at implementing the idea of "Healthy family - healthy society" in Uzbekistan, organizing targeted assistance to troubled families, educating young people to be spiritually rich and physically healthy, ensuring their employment, taking measures to strengthen the cooperation of citizens' self-governing bodies with state and non-state organizations in order to protect the young generation from ideological threats" [1. 23-39; 2. 218-221; 27] are being effectively applied which shows the institutionalization of youth competitiveness.

The family, as a social institution, serves primarily as a primary agent facilitating the socialization of young people, to ensure their introduction to various cultural processes. In particular, it creates an opportunity for young people to enter and compete in socio-cultural relations such as speech, distribution, and information exchange, relationship between adults and children, work, technology, profession. Therefore, in order to study the influence of family and family relations on the formation of competitive qualities in young people, it is appropriate to conduct sociological research using scientific methods on topics such as "An exemplary parent - a role model for young people", "Family environment in the formation of competitive qualities". Based on the conclusions of the scientific research of G. O. Ochilova, the researcher proved that "the content, strength and level of the attitudes formed in the adolescent youth who are raised in the family of entrepreneurs are directly related to the social environment that affects them, the interpersonal relations within the family, their positivity" [22. 16]. Researcher Sh. Sh. Negmatova notes, "One of the most important factors in the development of healthy competition in the conditions of a socially oriented market economy is the formation of a culture of competition. Achieving a culture of competition requires an increase in economic consciousness" [20. 15-16]. In our opinion, only economic awareness is lacking in achieving a competitive culture. After all, according to the sources, 15% of how a person grows up as a person depends on heredity, 40% on the environment, and the remaining 45% on the influence of education [18]. Therefore, in this process, family education acquires important practical importance. Family upbringing means the process of regular, consistent, ideological and spiritual influence of parents on the basis of their lives and lifestyles in order to form the foundations of worldview, political, moral, aesthetic and other social factors. However, it should not be forgotten that due to the development of our society, the family and all its life stages are undergoing serious changes. In this regard, T. Parsons, looking at the family as an institution that forms and changes the structure of the "socio-cultural sphere" of society, "it preserves normative cultural traditions and creates new ones. This is shared by all members of the society to one degree or another and is transmitted from generation to generation through the process of education [24].

The issue of proper formation of work skills in young people and making society members enjoy it is considered important. In this regard, Abdulla Avloni said: "Nowadays, it is necessary to acquire knowledge in order to achieve a goal, serve one's nation, and be acceptable to the people. All the states and powers of a person are measured by their possessions and wealth. Everywhere, the rich nations are like the master's son, and the poor are slaves and captives. In short, in order to become a person in accordance with the present time, an economy equal to knowledge and enlightenment, honesty, endless effort, endless extraordinary zeal are necessary in this regard" [15. 33].

All forms of human activity require constant work. Because in it, while gaining practical experience, a person thoroughly learns the secrets of his profession, materially and spiritually

encouraged. Therefore, the education system in our country, the integrity of education, is a great opportunity given to the youth of our country who have reached the age of adulthood, to become the owner of a certain profession, to work in this specialty at the next stages of their lives, or to further improve their skills. In particular, according to statistical data, during 2018-2020, a total of 1,002 talented and promising young people received the high status of scholarship holders of the "El-yurt umidi" (Hope of the Country) foundation and were sent to advanced foreign countries to study for bachelor's, master's and doctoral degrees. And most of them have completed their studies today, are working in various fields and are contributing to the development of our country. If you focus on data statistics, the "El-yurt umidi" Foundation has obtained education opportunities in more than 240 advanced universities, scientific centers and prestigious companies in 2021, and 420 in 2022 in a total of about 40 countries around the world, including the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, France, Japan, Canada, Italy, Spain, South Korea, China, Russia, by 2023 this figure is 490. In perspective, this figure is planned to increase even more. In particular, it is envisaged that opportunities will be created for the education of 560 young people in 2024, 630 in 2025 and 700 in 2026 on the basis of state grants in the undergraduate, master's and doctoral directions in the world's leading higher educational institutions [16. 4-8] . This serves to ensure that young people are competitive.

METHODOLOGY.

Research Design

We conducted a sociological questionnaire among young people in order to study the factors influencing the qualities of competitiveness in young people.

Sample and Data Collection

An empirical, frequent sociological survey was conducted and 723 people (n=723 people; 50.5% of respondents are men and 49.5% are women; 321 people live in the city (44.4%), 246 people (34%) live in rural areas, and 156 people (21.6%) live in the district center) participated.

FINDINGS / RESULTS.

According to the study, respondents were asked "Which of the following do you think will have a positive impact on the development of competitiveness?", 27% of respondents indicated that "initiative is supported", 12% indicated that "quality education is provided", and 15% indicated that "knowledge, skills, and skills are acquired". Next, 6% of respondents noted "level of professional competence", 7% efficiency and quality of labor activity, 11% fair choice in hiring personnel, 5% conditions created for the manifestation of personal and professional qualities, 5% appreciation of talents and abilities in a person, 2% motivation for self-development, 1% adherence to a healthy lifestyle, 8% wellness of the social environment, 1% family stability.

Figure 1. Which of the following do you think will have a positive effect on the development of competitiveness? classification of answers to the question:

The remaining respondents, on the other hand, believe that family stability, security assurance, labor community cohesion, the existence of a life strategy, work experience and professional training have a positive effect on the development of competitiveness, which the sisters believe (Figure 1).

Therefore, today's youth consider the "support of initiative" as a positive factor affecting the development of professional competitiveness, the "provision of quality education", and the "acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications".

In order to determine the negative factors affecting the development of professional competitiveness, "Which of the following do you think has a negative impact on the development of professional competitiveness?" to the question, 30% of the respondents mentioned corrupt situations, 21% inappropriate conflicts in labor activities, 14% low-quality education, 15% low-income work, 10% localism, tribalism, familiarity, 4% highly emotional stressful situations, 3% the leader's own they expressed their lack of understanding of the field and their harshness. 0.5 percent indicated that the tasks were not properly distributed by the leader, 1 percent indicated an unhealthy environment in an organization or higher educational institution, 0.1 percent indicated "personnel failure", 0.4 percent indicated "improper implementation of the incentive system", 0.5 percent indicated "insufficient labor conditions are not created" and 0.5 percent indicated "disdain for traditions and values" (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Which of the following do you think has a negative impact on the development of professional competitiveness? Classification of answers to the question

Therefore, most of the young people living in Uzbekistan believe that the development of professional competitiveness is negatively affected by factors such as corrupt situations, inappropriate conflicts in work, low-quality education, low-income work, localism, tribalism, familiarity.

Competition in the labor market affects the strategic behavior of young people and helps them to be competitive, which helps young people gain work experience and interact with labor market agents. This can be expressed as follows:

- the combination of work and study. On the one hand, employers prefer graduates with work experience, on the other hand, due to the "co-learning effect", employers engage in retraining of workers with low levels of education. In this regard, it will be necessary to increase the professional level of graduates with little work experience, and employers who cannot invest in young professionals will be less interested in hiring this category of workforce. In general, such a situation can lead to further devaluation of education for all participants of labor relations;

- behavioral competencies ("employability" and "marketability"). At the same time, the intensity of the job search and the efficiency of the search are related to shortening or increasing the

period of the job search, the period of finding a job that suits the needs of the person, etc. In this regard, Professor R. Samarov notes that "a person shows a pattern of behavior as a response to the influence of the environment and social institutions. They can be expressed in the following pattern: perceptual behavior pattern; in a pattern of defensive behavior; in an inductive behavior pattern; in a pattern of utilitarian behavior; role model; in a scripted pattern of behavior; in modeling behavior; in a pattern of depressed behavior; in a pattern of free behavior; in an attributive behavior pattern; in the pattern of expressive behavior; in an autonomous behavior pattern; in the sample of research behavior; in an affirmative behavior pattern; in empathetic behavior pattern, etc. [25. 40-43].

- mobility for jobs. For example, the theory of "job shopping" as a model of job search relies on the heterogeneity of information asymmetry in workers, jobs, and the labor market. Young professionals entering the labor market do not have a clear idea of what field they want to pursue a career in, they try themselves in completely different positions; as a result, they prefer the one that best suits their requirements. The theory of labor adaptation ("work adaptation theory") also arises from the existence of asymmetric information and is based on the fact that young professionals move through workplaces to choose a better match between their characteristics and the requirements of the workplace [8; 9]. The result of moving for jobs will continue until you find a suitable job. It is advisable to pay attention to the following aspects:

- requirements of the labor market (including regional and world labor markets) for education (is there a social order for professional specialization?);

- the purpose of professional education (why is training necessary?);

- the content of educational information (why should you teach?);

- teaching methods (on what order should be taught?);

- the identity of the teacher (what kind of person-expert should give a lesson?);

- the identity of the learner (in which specialty should the student become an expert-person?);

- demands and proposals of the employer (can the graduate work independently in practice after graduating from the educational institution?);

- the teacher's satisfaction with the teaching activity (is the pedagogue (coach) satisfied with the method used, the examples and comments given?);

- satisfaction of the learner with the educational activity (is the learner satisfied with his results, educational content, information and educational relations he receives?);

- the creation of an information space (has an information reserve been created in a specific space and its use regulated?);

- qualification improvement and professional retraining (which specializations are in increasing demand? which professional quality should be formed in specialists?) [26. 23-29] In turn, we can show this presented theoretical model as a social factor affecting the formation of professional competitiveness.

DISCUSSION.

O.V. Dushkina, who directly dealt with the issue of professional competitiveness, expresses it as follows:

"- a set of professional skills of a person as a subject of activity, his ability to apply these skills in practice in professional activity;

- a deep understanding of the content of one's work, as well as the form of professional activity due to the compatibility of this work with the important professional qualities of a person, his self-esteem, attitude to work;

- the skill level achieved by the person in the course of professional development;

- as a sum of mental qualities, a mental state that enables independent action, the ability to perform labor functions and having talent" [17].

CONCLUSION.

1. The qualities of professional competitiveness of young people are primarily related to the family factor, in which the professional choice is made, first of all, based on the life examples of family members, parents and close relatives. Also, the effectiveness of reforms in the field of

education affects the competitiveness of young people, which in turn is expressed at the functional, intellectual, situational, social and individual levels.

2. As a theoretical model of the formation of competitive qualities, "level of education quality ↔ level of health and well-being ↔ level of employment ↔ high wages ↔ level of conditions and opportunities created for young people ↔ citizenship position ↔ level of youth mobility ↔ level of gender equality ↔ security and we offer the level of ensuring stability ↔ the level of use of information and communication technologies ↔ the level of satisfaction of the needs of young people = ensuring the quality of competitiveness.

RECOMMENDATIONS.

To ensure professional competitiveness in young people, it is better to develop a national educational strategy and use the result of scientific research in those areas such as philosophy, sociology, psychology, law, medicine, economics. Also, taking into account that the labor market is directly related to other markets (for example, the capital market, the loan market, the commodity market, the securities market), it is necessary to carry out a dynamic analysis of the world labor market and establish the training of personnel in New specialties, ensuring the comprehensive development of the labor market. At the same time, the processes taking place in the labor market are leading to the autonomization of employment assistance services. In the process, it will be necessary to improve the professional education system, protecting national interests and setting the main directions of employment policy.

LIMITATIONS.

This study has some limitations. One of them asked about 20 questions to a group of university students. Not all of them are shown. The latter found that 75 percent of those who took part in an online survey considered themselves competitive. However, according to the results of the observations, in practice, it is possible to see that most of the young people do not find their place due to lack of competition or lack of jobs and other reasons. The next disadvantage is that Uzbekistan is a country whose population is constantly increasing, and no matter how much internal development it is, it will still rely on migration in the coming years. The study did not show the aspect of connection with labor migration.

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